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Utilizing student feedback for improving learning outcomes

Examples from a master course on ship vibrations

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ABSTRACT

Course evaluation has become standard in higher education organizations. However, when evaluation is not aligned to course design and development, its results are underused and its realization is rather routine than purpose driven. In order to improve student learning, a master course on ship vibrations at a German university was redesigned considering the conduction of online surveys at the beginning and end of the term. Starting point of the redesign of the here analyzed course was the observation that in preceding semesters students didn't perceive the course's practical relevance, showed poor motivation and didn't achieve satisfying levels of learning outcomes. Therefore, three new didactical elements were introduced: computer assisted assignments, lecture related home study assignments and guest lectures. Students were asked about motivation and prior knowledge in the beginning of the course and evaluated the new course elements, the course's professional relevance and their achievement of learning outcomes in the end. Linking the data via self-generated identification codes allowed us to assess intra-individual learning. The results show that there has been considerable improvement concerning the perceived professional relevance, but only moderate improvement regarding learning outcomes. This offers the opportunity for further development of the course. In the concept paper, we discuss different means of increasing professional relevance in naval architecture courses and describe the process of design, evaluation and redesign of this course, which can be seen as good practice for evidence-based teaching development.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Course evaluation has become standard in higher education organizations [1]. However, when evaluation is not aligned to course design and development, its results may be underused and its realization is rather routine than purpose driven. This may lead to discontent with the whole process of evaluating teaching and learning among both teachers and students. Its main purpose, to enable improvement of teaching and learning, may fall behind [2].

In order to improve student learning, a master course on ship vibrations at a German University of Technology has recently been redesigned. Starting point of the redesign were the results of previous course evaluations, where students reported a perceived lack of practical relevance of the course, and the observation that students showed poor motivation and didn't achieve satisfying levels of learning outcomes. Therefore, three new didactical elements were introduced: computer assisted assignments, lecture related home study assignments and guest lectures.

Following the idea of "system alignment" [2], the use of existing evaluation data and the collection of further feedback data from students was integrated into the process of the course's redesign. In addition to existing evaluation data from previous semesters, survey data were collected online at the beginning and end of the term. Students were asked about their motivation and prior knowledge in the beginning of the course. Furthermore, they evaluated the new course elements, the course's professional relevance and their achievement of learning outcomes in the end. Linking the survey data via self-generated identification codes allowed assessing intra-individual learning and change of attitudes towards the course [3]. These data were used to evaluate whether the introduction of the three new didactical elements had brought about the desired effects: an increase in professional relevance of the course perceived by students, an increase in students' motivation and a raise in levels of achieved learning outcomes.

In this concept paper, we describe the case of the course on ship vibrations and the point of departure for revising the course design. We discuss different means of increasing professional relevance, motivation and learning outcomes and explain our choice of new didactical elements. Moreover, we describe the process of design, evaluation and redesign of this course, integrating the collection and analysis of student feedback data. Aim of this article is to present one example of good practice for evidence-based teaching and learning development in engineering education.

2 REDESIGNING A MASTER'S COURSE ON SHIP VIBRATIONS

2.1 Context of the course

"Ship vibrations" is a mandatory weekly course in the first semester of the master program "Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering" at a German university of technology. It comprises a lecture and a recitation section and is normally attended by 20 to 30 students. The course aims to build up students' knowledge on the principles of ship vibrations, on its fundamental causes and sources that lead to non-comfort or even structural damage, on its consequences and possible mitigation methods. Concerning professional skills, it is the course's learning objective to enable students to detect vibration-prone components on ships, to model the structure by appropriate system analysis, to select and apply suitable calculation methods and to assess the results. Referring to social competencies, students are expected to be able to communicate and cooperate in a professional environment in

the shipbuilding and component supply industry after the course. All learning objectives have a clear emphasis on the professional relevance of the course.

2.2 Point of departure for redesigning the course

Originally, the course's syllabus was split into two parts that were conducted by two separate institutes. Due to insufficient coordination between the institutes and frequently changing teachers in the past, there was a lack of coherence of contents. Furthermore, previous course evaluations showed that students didn't perceive the course's contents as professionally relevant, and attributed the course with low levels of applicability for industrial processes. This clearly contradicted the course's learning objectives focused on professional relevance. Referring to Biggs' approach of constructive alignment, students did not perceive the course as meaningful for themselves [4]. This context probably explains the observation that students didn't show high motivation for the course and had unsatisfying examination results.

In the winter term of 2017 the course was handed over to one of the two institutes which offered the opportunity for redesigning the course by clearing up the courses syllabus and increasing coherence of contents. Moreover, there was an obvious need to align learning objectives, teaching methods and the final examination format. In cooperation with the university's center for teaching and learning, the teacher responsible for the course formulated three main goals for the redesign, referring to the initial situation described above:

- (A) to increase the practical relevance of contents and methods taught in the course and students' perception of it,
- (B) to increase students' motivation for the course, and
- (C) to enhance learning outcomes.

Referring to Edström's "desired outcomes of engineering education" [5], these goals touch several layers of outcomes and follow the overall aim to align educational and professional practice. Improving learning outcomes here refers to knowledge and skills improvement, application-orientation and the production of "graduate engineers capable of purposeful professional practice" [5]. In order to reach these goals, several teaching methods were considered to be implemented.

2.3 Concept for the redesign

Literature suggests several factors that motivate students in higher education. Establishing relevance, among other factors like "establishing interest" and "teaching for understanding" [6], is seen as central, so there is a strong relationship between students' perceptions of relevance and motivation. Especially, linking theory and practice and applying theory is seen as motivating for students [6]. Thus, creating professional relevance and including exercises, that give students the opportunity to assess their understanding, can be seen as tools increasing motivation.

Due to the digital transformation of society and industry, there's a strong need for engineering education to include new technologies into the curriculum [7]. Students are demanded to develop digital competences during their studies in order to be prepared for their future jobs. Digitalizing assignments and practicing with software that is used in relevant industries therefore can be seen as one way of creating professional relevance.

Another possible method of linking professional practice and theory in higher education is the inclusion of guest lectures into the curriculum. Guest lectures of professionals from industry or academia, who visit a course are seen as effective tool

for courses “with a clear industry relevance” [8], because they can “bring the real world into the classroom“ [9] and illustrate the professional relevance of course contents to students.

Based on these findings, we chose three didactical elements to be introduced to the course (see *Table 1*). In order to intertwine theoretical and methodological inputs with examples referring to professional real world problems, as a first step, in the first term after taking over responsibility for the course, alumni, practitioners and researchers from the field of naval architecture were invited to give guest lectures. The introduction of guest lectures should increase the practical relevance of the course, illustrate the applicability of contents taught in the course and thus raise the motivation of students. In addition to the guest lectures, optional lecture related home study assignments were offered to the students to give them the chance to self-assess their understanding prior to the final exam. These were intentionally kept of limited extend, in order to lower mental hurdles for the students to complete them.

In the second term after taking over responsibility for the course, obligatory computer assisted assignments were introduced to the recitation section. Both types of assignments should complement the calculation assignments that were conducted manually during the recitation sections, in order to deepen the students’ learning of contents and calculation methods and thereby better prepare them for the final exam. Moreover, by using software for calculations with finite elements, which is applied as a standard in marine industry, the introduction of computer assisted assignments was one means to increase the practical relevance of methods taught in the course.

Table 1. Redesigning the course: Introduction of new didactical elements

t ₀ (two separate institutes are in charge of the course; student cohort 0)	t ₁ (one institute takes over responsibility for the course; student cohort 1)	t ₂ (one year after restructuring responsibilities for the course; student cohort 2)
course is based on traditional teaching methods (lecture section: theoretical input phases by teachers from two institutes; recitation section: students work on calculation assignments manually)	(1) introduction of guest lectures to the lecture section (2) introduction of lecture related home study assignments	(maintenance of guest lectures in the lecture section and home study assignments) (3) introduction of computer assisted assignments in the recitation section

3 EVALUATION OF THE REDESIGN – UTILIZING STUDENT FEEDBACK DATA

In order to find out, whether the implementation of new didactical elements led to the desired effects, the evaluation of innovations was planned parallel to redesigning the course. In detail, the evaluation should answer the following questions:

- Do the guest lectures, computer assisted assignments and home study assignments lead to an increased professional relevance of the course perceived by students?
- Does the introduction of guest lectures, computer assisted assignments and home study assignments raise students’ motivation for the course?
- Do the computer assisted assignments and home study assignments help students to deepen their understanding of the course contents and finally lead to improved learning outcomes?

3.1 Method of data collection

The standard course evaluation conducted at this university at the end of every term offered first insights to opportunities for improvement of the course, but could only partly give answers to the questions formulated above. So it was decided to collect extra data. Since the three questions refer to a change in perceptions, affective and cognitive dispositions of students, we firstly decided to collect student survey data and secondly to collect data at several points in time, in order to address the timely component of the questions.

We conducted online surveys with “Limesurvey” – an online tool for which our university owns licenses – at three points in time. Survey (1) was conducted 18 months after student cohort 0 and six months after cohort 1 had finished the course. The second and third surveys were conducted with cohort 2 at the very start and end of the term (see *Table 2*).

Table 2. Evaluating the new didactical elements: Conduction of surveys

t ₀ (two separate institutes are in charge of the course; student cohort 0)	t ₁ (one institute takes over responsibility for the course; student cohort 1)	t ₂ (one year after restructuring responsibilities for the course; student cohort 2)
standard course evaluation data are collected at the end of the term	(maintenance of standard course evaluation) (1) online survey with students of cohort 0 (18 months after the end of the course) and students of cohort 1 (6 months after the end of the course)	(maintenance of standard course evaluation) (2) online survey with cohort 2 in the beginning of the term (3) online survey with cohort 2 at the end of the term

In the two surveys conducted with the second student cohort, students were asked to generate a personal identification code, which enabled us to compare the data from two points in time and assess intra-individual learning and change of attitudes towards the course, without identifying students as individual persons. We followed the recommendations given by Direnga et al. [3] for the design of the self-generated code, in order to enable matching a maximum of data. After having collected the data, they were analyzed with descriptive statistical methods.

3.2 Content of the online surveys

Focus of the survey conducted with the students of cohorts 0 and 1 was a self-assessment of the increase in knowledge on ship vibrations and programming skills attained during the course and an overall assessment of the professional relevance of the course. Since a successful stimulation of intrinsic interest is seen as a clear indicator for the establishment of relevance [6], we used sustainable interest in the topic of ship vibrations to grasp the motivational impact of the course. Students were asked whether it had inspired them to continue looking into the topic of ship vibrations in future. In addition, some open-ended questions gave the students the opportunity to give feedback on what aspects of the course helped them learn, what impeded their learning, and what suggestions for improved learning in the course they had. In addition to that, cohort 1 was asked to evaluate the guest lectures referring to their contribution to the professional relevance of the course and the

home study assignments referring to their helpfulness for understanding the topics of the course.

The first survey with the students of cohort 2 was conducted during the very first session of the course. We collected data on the students' self-assessment of knowledge on ship vibrations and programming skills before the start of the course, on their perceptions of the overall professional relevance of the course in advance, their motivation and their expectations for the course. Focus of the second survey with this cohort of students, conducted in a session one week before the end of the course, was a self-assessment concerning the achievement of learning objectives, especially the attainment of knowledge on ship vibrations and programming skills, again an overall assessment of the professional relevance of the course and an evaluation of the guest lectures, the home study assignments and the computer assisted assignments referring to their impact on the professional relevance of the course and on understanding. Again, as an indicator for motivation, students were asked about their intentions to keep in touch with the topic of ship vibrations in future and for their open feedback on learning conditions within the course.

4 RESULTS

The response rate of cohorts 0 and 1 was quite low ($n_0=8$, $n_1=3$) which can be explained by the fact that it was conducted many months after the students had finished the course. Their interest to give feedback after such a long time is assumed to be rather low, while others might have left the university already. Due to the high selectivity of responders, the results of this survey have to be interpreted very carefully. Compared to that, the response rates of cohort 2 were satisfactory due to the conduction of the surveys during lecture time ($n_{2.start}=19$, $n_{2.end}=18$). Unfortunately, only nine cases could be matched on the base of the self-generated codes, so we could only measure intra-individual learning and change of attitudes for nine students.

In order to answer the questions formulated above, the results of all surveys are sorted by the three main goals of the redesign: the perceived professional relevance by students, their motivation and their understanding of course contents.

4.1 Professional relevance perceived by students

After having finished the course, students from all cohorts were asked to rate the relevance of the course for their professional career on an 11-point-scale from 0 (not relevant at all) to 10 (very relevant). In addition to that, the students of cohort 2 were asked the same question in advance ("In general, how relevant will the course be [*resp.: was the course*] for your professional career in your opinion?"). Students from cohort 0, who had neither experienced guest lectures nor computer assisted assignments or home study assignments, attested the lowest perceived relevance with a mean of 5.88. Students of cohort 1, who had experienced guest lectures and home study assignments, report an average relevance of 9.0, but this average is only based on the answers of two students. Students of cohort 2 reported an average perceived relevance of 6.6 at the start and 7.4 at the end of the term. Interestingly, matching the data from both surveys, shows that there has nearly been no intra-individual change of perceived relevance. For those students whose data could be matched, only an average individual change of -0.33 scale points is measurable. So they even stated a slightly lower perceived relevance after having finished the course.

The evaluation of guest lectures concerning their professional applicability and relevance shows quite satisfactory results for cohort 2, whereas only one person from cohort 1 answered the relevant questions. Nearly all students from cohort 2 agree totally or partly, that the guest lectures showed applications of the topics of the course in different fields and that they were useful to understand the relevance of the course for their professional career (see *Figure 1*).

Figure 1. Evaluation of the guest lectures: Answers of cohort 2 (n=18)

“The guest lectures of alumni and scientists...
...showed applications of the topics of the
course in different fields.”

...were useful to understand the relevance
of the course for my professional career.”

4.2 Students’ motivation

All students were asked, whether the course inspired them to continue looking into the topic in future (see *Figure 2*).

Figure 2. “The course inspired me to continue looking into the topic in future.”
Answers of cohort 0 (n=8), cohort 1 (n=2) and cohort 2 (n=18)

The answers to this question can be interpreted as an indicator for how motivating the course was for students referring to how interesting the contents are still after having finished the course. The results show that whereas a majority (87.5 %) of students from cohort 0 partly or totally disagree that the course inspired them, all students from cohort 1 and a majority of students from cohort 2 (77.8 %) agreed partly or totally, that the course inspired them.

4.3 Students’ understanding of contents

Several questions were asked in all surveys to find out how students self-assessed their personal knowledge and skills development during the course. Students from

cohorts 0 and 1 were asked in retrospect whether their knowledge and skills increased during the course from their point of view (on a 4-point agreement scale). Students from cohort 2 were asked to self-assess their knowledge and skills levels on an 11-point scale in the beginning of the course and at the end. By that it was possible to calculate the difference between the two points in time.

Concerning the development of knowledge in mechanical vibrations, the first two cohorts already show positive results – in both cohorts all students agree totally or partly that their knowledge in mechanical vibrations increased during the course. This result can also be found, analyzing the data from cohort 2. Asked to estimate their level of knowledge in mechanical vibrations on a scale from 0 (no knowledge at all) to 10 (extensive knowledge on a high scientific level), students located themselves on average at 4.6 in the beginning of the course and at 6.5 in the end. Matching the data from both surveys shows an average rise in scale points of 2.2.

The results for the self-assessment of programming skills are quite different. Whereas more than half of the students from cohort 0 and 1 disagree partly or totally that their programming skills increased during the course, a slight rise in estimated programming skills can be seen for cohort 2. On a scale from 0 (no skills at all) to 10 (extensive skills on a professional level), they located their programming skills at 3.4 in the beginning and at 4.6 in the end of the course. The average intra-individual rise in scale points lies at 1.0.

Besides the overall self-assessment of knowledge and skills, we wanted to find out whether there was a positive impact of the new didactical elements on the students' understanding of course contents from their point of view. Being asked whether the guest lectures helped understand the course contents, at least half of the students in both cohorts 1 and 2 partly or totally agreed. A bigger majority of at least 92 % of the students of cohorts 1 and 2 agreed partly or totally that the home study assignments helped understand the topics of the course. However, being asked whether they improved their programming skills because of the home study assignments, at least half of the students in both cohorts disagreed partly or totally. The results are slightly more positive concerning the computer assisted assignments, which were only offered to cohort 2. 92 % of the students agreed partly or totally that the computer assisted assignments helped them understand the topics of the course and 69.3 % agreed partly or totally that they extended their skills-set because of the computer assisted assignments.

Further indication for the usefulness of the assignments was given within the open comments where students gave their feedback on the overall learning conditions of the course. Both in cohort 1 and 2, students emphasized the helpfulness of the exercises for their learning and advised to include even more computer assisted and home study assignments in the course.

The positive feedback is also partly reflected in the grades of the final exam. The exam results of all three cohorts are displayed in *Figure 3*. With an increase of didactical methods (from cohort 0 to 2) the percentage of better grades increased as well. Especially in cohort 2, a higher percentage of students passed the exam. However, it remains to be investigated in the coming courses whether the indicated improvement is due to the positive effect of teaching methods or due to natural variation.

Figure 3: Distribution of grades of the three evaluated cohorts in the final exam

5 DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

The results of the surveys give a mostly positive picture concerning the evaluation of the new didactical elements. On average, those students who experienced guest lectures, home study and computer assisted assignments perceive the course as more professionally relevant than those who did not. A majority of students from cohort 2 agree that the guest lectures have beneficial effects on the professional applicability and relevance of the course. More students stated that they were inspired to keep up with the topic of ship vibrations, when they experienced guest lectures, home study assignments and computer assisted assignments, compared to students who did not. Referring to students' understanding of course contents – both knowledge of mechanical vibrations and programming skills rise during the course, speaking for cohort 2 – it cannot be said without doubt that the new didactical elements played a central role here. Moreover, both relevant knowledge and skills remain on a fairly low level, so the course design can still be improved.

However, one lesson we learned concerning the new didactical elements is that the guest lectures play an especially important role. Basic data analysis (see *Figure 4*) and experience from the course leads us to the assumption that the guest lectures' impact might be rather high.

Figure 4. "(...) helped me understand the topics of the course."
 Answers of cohort cohort 2 (n=18 for guest lectures; n=13 for assignments)

Compared to the other two course elements, the highest percentage of students (94.5 %) agrees totally or partly that the guest lectures helped them understand the topics of the course. We consider the guest lectures to be highly effective because

they facilitate students' access to the course topic, especially because they were held by guests from industry and former students of the course, they enable students to better understand course contents, raise their motivation and activate them.

Generally speaking, a positive impact of the new didactical elements on all three goals – perceived professional relevance, motivation and, with limited validity, deeper understanding – can be assumed on the base of the data analyzed. However, we find that the study methodology still needs to be adjusted to better serve our study objectives. The longitudinal survey design we applied for cohort 2 is a first step towards more clarity about the impact of the didactical innovations on learning outcomes. But still, even in this case, we cannot eliminate the impact of unobserved factors that might have had an influence on all three goals, like learning in other courses or more personal factors of the students [10]. Moreover, out of 19 respondents from the first survey only nine could be matched with the data from the second survey, so we only had evidence on intra-individual learning for very few persons. Thus, since we are planning to continue analyzing learning outcomes in this course, firstly, we will have to think about further possible factors of influence, and secondly about an evaluation of the adequacy of the self-generated code format.

To find out more about students' understanding and learning outcomes, as a next step, the examination format will also have to be evaluated concerning its alignment with learning objectives and teaching methods.

Learning outcomes, assessed by students themselves, have improved in this course, but results also show that the didactical design of the course and its evaluation need further development. Still, the students' feedback we received via a number of surveys gave us detailed information that will help us to create “a meaningful and motivational context” [5] for students, and the methods we applied to design, evaluate and redesign the course can be seen as one example for evidence-based teaching development.

REFERENCES

- [1] Spooren, P., Brockx, B. and Mortelmans, D. (2013), On the Validity of Student Evaluation of Teaching: The State of the Art, *Review of Educational Research*, Vol. 83, No. 4, pp. 598-642.
- [2] Edström, K. (2008), Doing course evaluation as if learning matters most, *Higher Education Research & Development*, Vol. 27, No. 2, pp. 95-106.
- [3] Direnga, J., Timmermann, D., Lund, J. and Kautz, C. (2016), Design and Application of Self-Generated Identification Codes (SGICs) for Matching Longitudinal Data, Proceedings of the 44th SEFI Annual Conference, Tampere (Finland).
- [4] Biggs, J. (2003), Aligning teaching for constructing learning, *Higher Education Academy*. Available online: <https://www.heacademy.ac.uk/knowledge-hub/aligning-teaching-constructing-learning> (30.04.2019).
- [5] Edström, K. (2012), Student feedback in engineering: a discipline-specific overview and background, in: Nair, C. S., Patil, A. and Mertova, P. (eds.), *Enhancing Learning and Teaching Through Student Feedback in Engineering*. Chandos Publishing, Oxford, pp. 1-23.

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- [6] Kember, D., Ho, A. and Hong, C. (2008), The importance of establishing relevance in motivating student learning, *Active Learning in Higher Education*, Vol. 9, No. 3, pp. 249-263.
- [7] OECD (2019), Trends Shaping Education 2019, OECD Publications, Paris. Available online: <http://www.oecd.org/education/trends-shaping-education-22187049.htm> (30.04.2019).
- [8] Krogstie, B. R. and Krogstie, J. (2018), Guest lectures in IT education – recommendations based on an empirical study, *Norsk Konferanse For Organisasjoners Bruk av Informasjonsteknologi*. Available online: <https://ojs.bibsys.no/index.php/Nokobit/article/view/554/473>.
- [9] Riebe, L., Sibson, R., Roepen, D. and Meakins, K. (2013), Impact of industry guest speakers on business students' perceptions of employability skills development, *Industry & Higher Education*, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 55-66.
- [10] Pohlenz, P., Niedermeier, F., Erdmann, M. and Schneider, J. (2016), Studierendenbefragungen als Panelstudie. Potenziale des Einsatzes von Längsschnittdaten in der Evaluation von Lehre und Studium, in: Großmann, D. and Wolbring, T. (eds.), *Evaluation von Studium und Lehre. Grundlagen, methodische Herausforderungen und Lösungsansätze*. Springer VS, Wiesbaden, pp. 289-320.